

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

ALGEBRA IN THE "TEACHING PROCESS ON THE FACE CIRCLE" IN PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHING ELEMENTS TECHNOLOGY

Ibrahimov F.N.,

Professor,

Sheki branch of ADPU

Aliyeva G.O.

Teacher,

Sheki branch of ADPU

Abstract

The article reveals the nature of the "system-structural" approach, reflects the dependence of mathematics taught in the elementary grades on the integer with which the lines of content are contained, and the technology of teaching elements of algebra on the hundred circle, which rests on the dialectics between the lines of content. During the development of this technology, the focus was on expanding and deepening the considered problems related to numerical and variable expressions, equations and their solutions. It was also taken into account that the units of length, the study of the relationship between them, during the numbering of numbers in the Hundred circle, reinforce algebraic propedavtics.

Keywords: numbering; numerical and variable expressions; "Living mathematical expressions"; parentheses; the value of the expression; equations and inequalities; measurement; length.

Relevance of the research topic. The technology of teaching algebraic elements on the face circle, based on the complete dependence of the content lines of mathematics taught in secondary schools and the dialectic of their subsystems, has not been developed, the effectiveness of which has a significant impact on the subsequent results of teaching mathematics. This "theoretical gap" creates conditions for the existence of errors in the relevant activities of practical educators, which is especially evident in the work of young professionals. Therefore, we claim the relevance of the research topic we have chosen for the approach we have taken as a basis.

Interpretation of research materials. A so-called "system-structural" approach to events and objects, their perception is a characteristic feature of modern times. This methodological approach "resonates" with L. Bertalanfi's idea of system-analysis.

According to this idea, in order to consider a research object as a system, it must meet the following requirements:

1. The object must consist of (complete) subsystems (parts);
2. The integration of subsystems into a single system should help to establish the problem correctly (for the purpose of the research layer);
3. The system must have a property that determines the interaction of subsystems;
4. The system must be part of a larger system (subsystem). [8; 203]

The "system-structural" approach, which has proven itself as an important methodological method, has become so fashionable that there is even a tendency to evaluate it as an alternative to the dialectical method. In our opinion, the correct position here is that the "system-structural" method is a branch of development of the dialectical method that is able to keep pace with the scientific and technological progress of our time. we

are talking about a deeper study of the attitude of the part.

In the recent past, the debates in the philosophical literature about the categories of "complete-part", "system-element" and their relationship to each other have slowed down, but there are still differences of opinion on some aspects. Most philosophers are of the opinion that a system is a union of the interrelationships of the elements that make it up, and by its logical scope it belongs to a genre (type) of general concepts that can be applied to any object, event or process. "Complete" and "system" are often explained by a "species-gender" relationship, sometimes acting as a synonym, noting that they reflect different aspects of the same object. Sometimes it is considered the pinnacle of a fledgling system. There are also attempts to include systems and elements in the polar categories of dialectics. [9; 217]

According to the most common view of the whole and the part, the part of the system is a component that is part of the building and has relative independence, a system that completely covers the interconnected parts and has some properties that are not always present in the individual parts.

As you can see, we use the concept of system in the definition of full and part. Just as the system is complete, the part and the element are interrelated. Here we support an undisputed view: the system is complete, containing both the elements and the relationships between the elements; When we move away from the unity of the elements of the system and focus on the relationship between them, we come to the concept of the structure of the system. Here the element acts as a relatively indivisible part of the whole. The interaction of the whole with the part finds its expression both in the dependence of the quality of the whole on the specific nature of the parts that make it up, and in the dependence of the quality of these parts on the specific nature of the whole. The organic unity of the elements and their relations, which act as a

relatively indivisible part of the whole, is characterized by the concept of a system. The dialectical unity of the elements and the structure (the dialectical connection of the whole with the part is in fact the structure of the whole, in this sense, the structure acts as one of the important ways of the existence of the whole) is the main feature of the system.

Systematic research pays more attention to the epistemological aspect of the problem - the organization and structure of knowledge in the system. However, the nature of the system as a whole depends not only on its material and ideal existence, but also on the organization and structure of its substrate - the elements that make it up. [8; 106]

The essence of the system is determined by its structure and function, ie the nature of the relationship between the elements and their behavior, the specificity of the relationship of the object to the situation. It is impossible to distinguish the continuous, important, necessary connections here without studying the elements that make up the system and their interaction. Such a continuous, necessary interaction of elements characterizes the structure of the system. The law of relationships of structural elements acts as an invariant of the system. Both the function of the system and the functions of each element in relation to the whole remain in the shadows without studying or revealing the complete connection of the elements that they form.

The full concept is related to the system, it is the organization of the system. Each system has its own structure and the function that this structure carries. The system can be considered as a whole, consisting of a combination of its structure and function.

In spite of the above, we claim that the process of teaching mathematics in primary school is complete, the process of mastering the knowledge, skills and habits separated by content lines is complete. Therefore, we considered it acceptable to conduct the research process according to the presented approach. Based on this approach, we consider it appropriate to define "technology of teaching algebraic elements" in the process of teaching "Circle of Hundred" as a summary of research materials obtained in the following figure, and we believe that this technology has superior advantages.

In preparation for solving complex problems, students become familiar with the expressions included in parentheses. The parentheses need to be used in the future to write complex solutions in numerical formulas, as well as to determine the properties of arithmetic operations. [6]

The "parentheses" sign is given at this stage of the training as a sign that this or that arithmetic operation is performed on any mathematical expression, not on individual numbers. For example, you need to add the sum of 3 and 6 on top of 10; in this case, it is written in parentheses to indicate that the total must be added. [12; 109]

To understand this role of parentheses, children need to understand that the terms "sum" and "difference" have two meanings: sum and difference are not only the results of actions, but also expressions ($10 + 4 = 14$, where 14 and $10 + 4$ are sums). Even in

the teaching of the first ten, children became acquainted with two meanings of the term "sum". When they learn to number the second decimal number, they learn that in the example of $10 - 7 = 3$, there is no difference not only in the number 3, but also in the expression $10 - 7$. Later, special efforts are given to strengthen that knowledge.

Later, when students perform new preparatory work, they learn that it is possible to add and subtract and add or subtract. For example, the following exercises are given for oral work: subtract 3 from the sum of 4 and 5, add the difference of 6 and 4 on top of 10, and so on. By performing these and similar exercises orally, children show which action they perform first and which action they perform second. [13; 119-121]

A system of exercises should be used to develop the ability of primary school students to use the parentheses in a clear manner. An example of such an exercise in the first place, which is included in the system, can be: "Subtract the sum of 2 and 5 out of 10". After the students have solved this task orally, the teacher explains how to write the following examples: $10 - (2 + 5)$. Students are then asked to solve relevant exercises as well as parentheses. Each time the children read the expressions and explain what the parentheses indicate.

In the teaching of the topic "Numbering in a hundred circles" it is necessary to strengthen the knowledge of the relationship between the components and the result in the operation of addition (finding the unknown addition). There are enough examples and problems in this regard in the textbooks used in different academic years [1-5], and the teacher can benefit from them and, if necessary, by compiling additional examples of finding unknown collections.

When solving them, students should be asked to state the appropriate rule each time. If individual students have difficulty choosing an action, they should work with them again and again, using didactic materials. Thanks to this kind of work, the connection between the group and those gathered is consciously discovered by the students. These students should not be required to memorize the rule, as they will formally master the rule without knowing the interaction. [11; 296-297]

At this stage, the number of observations revealing the relationship between the components and the results of addition and subtraction operations continues to increase, the sum is not smaller than each of the aggregates, the difference is not greater than the decrement, not less than the decrement. For this purpose, studies on the comparison of sum and sum, or difference and subtraction, selection of the transmitted "plus" or "minus" sign, observations on tables, etc. is offered. It is also useful to draw children's attention to the cases where the sum and subtraction are equal to zero, while it is shown that the sum is not always greater than the sum and can be equal to it, and the difference is not always smaller than the decrement, and can be equal to it. Also, at this stage, it is not necessary to express these relations in general, only individual facts should be considered. [10; 54]

Knowledge about these relationships is used in studies relating to the comparison of expressions in a general way. For example, when comparing the number 7 with the expression $3+7$, children first compare the sum $(7+3)$ with the number (7), on the basis of which the required sign is written (the sum is greater than the sum), then check the correctness of the sign, calculating the result $(10>7)$. But children with poor training can calculate the total and compare the obtained numbers with the easiest way for them.

In the learning phase we are focusing on, we must continue to observe the change in the sum and the difference depending on the change in one of the components of the addition and subtraction operation. [10; 55]. It is obvious that in this regard, children do not briefly state any rules (this can happen at a later stage). But in each case, they must see the nature of change.

For example, one of the congregations has not changed, the other has shrunk, and the sum has shrunk; the question of how many loneliness or shrinking the sum or difference has not yet been given at this stage. True, some children who have mastered the properties of such changes use this knowledge in the implementation of special exercises (exercises related to the comparison of specially selected examples, tables, expressions). For example, children define relationships by comparing $36+3$ and $36+4$, $90-10$ and $90-20$ and such expressions, first comparing the results; ($39<40$), So $36+3<36+4$ and the like), and then they use the formed knowledge (3 is smaller than 4, the first is the same, so $36+3$ is smaller than $36+4$. In this case, the calculations necessary for verification are made (written or oral).

Finally, during the study of numbering, it is necessary to improve students' knowledge of terms: the names of components or results of operations. For this purpose, the teacher should use these terms frequently, and also give children different tasks that require them to use the terms frequently (students read examples in different ways, write down problems to be solved in writing, etc.) [7; 21]

While getting acquainted with the properties of operations and calculation methods (in the first grade), children encounter a "chain of equality" ($34 + 20 = (30 + 4) + 20 = (30 + 20) + 4 = 50 + 4 = 54$). The structure of the expressions (which are proposed for comparison) gradually becomes more complex. In the second grade, instead of the term "mathematical expression", a shorter term—"expression" is used (also the term "value of an expression" is used) at the stage of generalization and systematization of the studied materials. At this time, the formula of the tasks for children corresponds to this: "write down the phrase and calculate its price", "compare phrases", etc. After that, students get the opportunity to get acquainted with the finding of the sum of two expressions, and then with readings, spellings, comparisons of more complex expressions on the deduction of the sum from the sum by various methods.

By the way, as new properties are discovered, it is important to compare them and the corresponding computational techniques with those previously studied. This kind of work not only helps to better

master the properties and computational techniques, but also prevents many errors. For example, in order not to confuse the properties of numerical subtraction from the sum with the property of subtraction of numbers from the sum, computational methods based on these properties are offered to compare these properties themselves and similar calculation methods: "Compare examples and their solutions: $(30 + 10) - 5$ and $30 - (10 + 5)$, $82-50$ and $80-52$." For the sake of justice, we must say that in the textbooks used in our schools in different years, there are quite similar studies on the comparison of examples and methods of their solution. [1-5]. Besides, similar examples are given in turn and do not need to be compared. This forces the student to make an independent comparison and choose the appropriate solution for each example.

Familiarity with the rules related to the sequence of first- and second-level actions is a new step in expanding children's familiarity with various structural numerical expressions. It is necessary to apply special and systematic work for students to master the explanations related to the procedure for performing arithmetic operations in complex expressions and taking into account the parentheses in the application of these rules. Different terms should not be used to avoid additional difficulties. [10; 56]

There is enough material in the textbooks published in different years to organize the work of mastering these rules. [1-5]. Teachers should be able to complete them on specific topics. The application of the following content and required tasks is useful for this stage of training.

*Determine the position of the brackets so that the following equations are correct: and so on. $36 : 4 + 5 \cdot 2 = 8$; $12 + 6 : 2 + 2 = 11$; $24 - 12 : 4 + 2 = 23$

*Identify the missed action sign: $12 * 6 * 3 = 6$; $12 * 6 * 3 = 30$.

It is effective to use sample pairs that illustrate different instances of a sequence of actions. For example, $4 + 6 * 3$ and $4 * 6 + 3$, $16 : 2 + 5 * 3$, $16 + 2 * 5 - 3$.

In this case, the expression in the first example should be read as follows: add the product of four numbers 6 and 3; sum the product of four and 6 and 3.

Undoubtedly, students have difficulty reading complex expressions. However, overcoming this difficulty is not a difficult task. A student who is able to determine the order of actions is able to read the expression correctly. There is an internal connection between these two issues. [10; 57]

A new fundamental step for students in working on expression is to become familiar with one or two variables. "Variable expression" is the topic of a special session. Prior to this lesson, some preparatory work had been done in the process of teaching the "Circle of Ten" to acquaint students with the variable and the expression with the variable. It is useful to use the game "Live Mathematical Expressions" when getting acquainted with two-variable mathematical expressions.

The game "Live Mathematical Expressions" is performed as follows:

Three students are called to the blackboard; one of them is given a card with 10 numbers written on it,

another with a "plus" sign written on it, and the third is given, for example, a card with 8 numbers written on it; those students line up and raise their cards.

M: What mathematical expression do you see? (Sum: the sum of -10 and 8).

After that, three more students are called, and in the same way other sets, for example, $7 + 7$; $15 + 4$; $40 + 34$ is compiled. The summoned trinity is lined up in front of the previous trinity, and the children read each new expression.

M: How many mathematical expressions have we compiled? (4). Can we compile again? How many? In what ways do these expressions fit? Name the first collected numbers (10,7, 15,40).

We know that many such mathematical expressions can be compiled, and then there may be other numbers that are collected first. Instead of writing different numbers, you can use any number that can be added first, for example, a letter: a

The teacher shows a card with a a letter written on it. The summoned student stands in front of a letter with a letter indicating the first collection, in front of the students holding cards with numbers in their hands.

In this way, the teacher shows a card with a letter written on it b . The summoned student stands in front of a letter with a letter indicating the first collection, in front of the students holding cards b with numbers in their hands.

M: What did we denote by the letter a ? what did we denote by the letter b ?

M: - Raise the cards(the students who stand in front of the cards marked with the letter a are indicated) and indicate which numbers can be denoted with a (the students make cards).These numbers are numerical values of the letter a .

M: - Raise the cards(with the letter b , the students standing in front of the cards drawn are indicated) and indicate which numbers can be denoted with b (pupils raise the cards).These numbers are the values of the letter b .

M: Is it possible to give other numerical values to the letter a ? (Possible). For example, which ones? (The students say several numbers). Now write a mathematical expression with the help of letters (the called student takes a card with "plus" written on it and stands among the students with a and b cards in their hands)

The sum of the numbers a and b is indicated here. Children sing in chorus: the sum of the numbers a and b . Specific examples are given:

* $a = 10, b = 8$ If so, what mathematical expression do we get? Show on the cards (children show: $10 + 8$).

* The teacher then says other values of a and b , and the students standing by the cards show the corresponding sum.

Work on mathematical expressions continues in the next lesson. In this lesson, it is necessary to continue the work on reading mathematical expressions and calculating their value according to the given values of the letters included in the expressions. For this purpose, it is necessary to work on properly selected and systematized studies.

The work on solving equations in the "Hundred Circles" educational unit is significantly complicated. In the "Circle of Ten" unit, students were mainly involved in solving equations using the relationship between the components and results of addition and subtraction. In the process of teaching in this direction, the equations performed in connection with these actions are more complex in structure. Here it is expedient to dwell on the equations in the following structure:

$$x + 5 = 38 - 20; 17 - x = 50 - 30;$$

$(18 + 22) + x = 50; (16 + x) - 34 = 10$ and so on.

Students do not have much difficulty working with the equations presented here in the first three forms. However, working on the equations presented in the fourth form poses difficulties for students. and so on. Conducting special exercises on the solution of equations in the form of gives good results. In order to prepare students for the solution of such equations, it is necessary to train them to compile, read, write and solve parentheses, which in the following points are unknown numbers, and so on. can help you compose and read expressions in the form of. When reading such expressions, students should indicate to which component the unknown belongs, for example, the first component (decreasing) in the expression is the sum of 30 unknown numbers, minus 18, ie the unknown number belongs to the decrementer. Then it is easy to move on to the method of solving the equations, which is expressed on one side: one or two equations are solved with the active intervention (guidance) of the teacher, and then students focus on the implementation of relevant tasks in the conditions of independence. The following examples can be used in this study:

$$(12 - x) + 10 = 18, 50 + (x - 14)$$

$$= 56(30 + x) - 18(30 + x) - 18$$

$$40: b = 2; a: 2 = 32; 16 + x = 26 + 16; 35 + x = 5 \cdot 7;$$

$$a - 10 = 40: 8; x \cdot 6 = 34 - 28; (5 - c) + 40 =$$

$$40; 100 - (50 + k) = 50;$$

$$(10 - x) + 10 = 20 \text{ and so on.}$$

Of research scientific innovation. The technology of "Teaching algebraic elements on the face circle" was developed on the basis of the dependence of the content lines and the dialectic between the content lines on the emergent nature of the system of teaching mathematics in secondary schools.

Practical research importance. The scientific novelty of the research will have a positive impact on the work of practical educators to eliminate possible mistakes in the process of assimilation of "algebraic elements of the face circle" to students.

The result. The dependence of the emergent nature of the mathematics teaching system in secondary schools on the emergent nature of its content lines and the assimilation of algebraic elements based on the dialectic between the content lines have a positive effect on the achievement of effective results.

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